

Public Perceptions of Physician Board Certification and Board Eligibility in the United States

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Abstract

Background: Physician credentials play a central role in patient trust and decision-making. While medical licensure and board certification are distinct processes, the public's understanding of these credentials, particularly the meaning of *board eligible*, remains unclear. The purpose of this study was to assess U.S. adults' beliefs and expectations regarding physicians' professional development, their understanding of medical licensure and board certification, and their perceptions of the term *board eligible*.

Methods: This study involved a cross-sectional national survey consisting of 806 U.S. adults recruited through Amazon Mechanical Turk. Participants completed an online survey assessing expectations of physician competence, knowledge of licensure and board certification, and awareness and interpretation of *board eligible*. Post-stratification weights based on 2017 U.S. Census benchmarks for age, sex, and race were applied. Weighted descriptive analyses were conducted.

Results: Weighted analyses showed strong public expectations that physicians remain current and demonstrate ongoing professional development. Board certification was widely viewed as important and as increasing confidence in physicians. By contrast, interpretations of *board eligible* varied substantially, and no single understanding predominated, indicating widespread public confusion.

Conclusions: The public holds strong and consistent expectations regarding physicians' professional development and views board certification as an important indicator of trust and competence. By contrast, the term *board eligible* is interpreted inconsistently and often ambiguously. These findings highlight a disconnect between professional credentialing terminology and public understanding, with implications for transparency, communication, and professional self-presentation in medicine.

Introduction

Physician credentials play a central role in shaping public perceptions of competence, professionalism, and trust in medical care. In the United States, two credentialing processes are most visible to patients: medical licensure and board certification. Medical licensure, administered by state medical boards, is a legal requirement that establishes minimum qualifications for the practice of medicine and defines scope of practice. Licensure verifies completion of accredited training and passage of a general examination but does not certify specialty-specific expertise.¹⁻³

Board certification, by contrast, is a voluntary, specialty-specific process intended to demonstrate advanced knowledge and skills beyond licensure requirements. Specialty certification in the United States emerged in the early twentieth century in response to variability in postgraduate training and practice standards and was later consolidated under the American Board of Medical Specialties (ABMS) to promote consistency and public trust.⁴⁻⁶ Certification has historically served as an important mechanism of professional self-regulation, reinforcing medicine's responsibility to assure competence and accountability to the public.⁷

A substantial literature has examined the relationship between board certification and quality of care. Prior observational research has linked board certification to higher-quality care processes, greater adherence to evidence-based guidelines, and improved patient outcomes, particularly among hospital-based and early-career physicians.⁸⁻¹⁰ Although causal relationships are difficult to establish, these findings have contributed to the widespread use of board certification in hospital privileging, payer credentialing, and physician employment decisions.

Research has also examined patient perceptions of board certification. Early population-based studies found that patients view board certification as an important indicator of physician competence, even though awareness of their physician's actual certification status is often imperfect.¹¹ Subsequent surveys have consistently shown that patients report greater trust and confidence in board-certified physicians and place value on certification when selecting a doctor.¹²⁻¹⁴ These findings suggest that board certification functions not only as a measure of professional qualification but also as a symbolic signal of quality and credibility to the public.

By contrast, much less is known about public understanding of the designation "board eligible." Historically, board eligibility referred to a defined period following completion of accredited residency training during which a physician could sit for an initial specialty board examination. Over time, variations in policies across certifying boards have contributed to ambiguity in how the term is defined and used.¹⁵

Concerns about public misunderstanding of *board eligible* have led some regulators to restrict its use in physician advertising. For example, the Texas Medical Board has prohibited the use of terms such as "board eligible" and "board qualified," concluding that such language may be misleading and cause confusion regarding certification status.¹⁶ Legal and professional analyses of physician advertising similarly emphasize that credentialing language must be truthful, verifiable, and not misleading to patients, highlighting the potential for misinterpretation when credential terms lack standardized meaning.¹⁷

Despite these regulatory concerns, empirical research directly examining how patients interpret the term *board eligible* is limited. Much of the existing literature addresses board eligibility from professional or institutional perspectives rather than public understanding. Moreover, prior studies of public perceptions of physician credentials have often relied on convenience samples or sponsorship by certifying organizations, raising questions about framing and generalizability.

To address these gaps, the present study provides an assessment of U.S. adults' beliefs and expectations regarding physicians' professional development, their understanding of medical licensure and board certification, and their perceptions of the term *board eligible*. Using a national online survey with post-stratification weighting to U.S. Census benchmarks, this study seeks to clarify how physician credentialing language is understood by the public and to inform discussions about transparency and professional communication in medicine.

Methods

Participants and Procedures

Data were collected via an electronic survey administered to U.S. adults recruited through Amazon Mechanical Turk (mTurk; Amazon.com, Inc., Seattle, Washington), a crowdsourcing Internet marketplace. All participants were compensated a nominal fee. Amazon mTurk was selected because prior research demonstrates that mTurk workers provide reliable, high-quality survey data and constitute a socioeconomically and culturally diverse pool of respondents.¹⁸⁻²⁰ Eligibility criteria required participants to be at least 18 years old and residents of the United States. A total of 806 participants completed the survey, yielding a nominal margin of error of approximately 2.99% at the 95% confidence level. Although mTurk samples are non-probability samples, this benchmark facilitates comparison with national public opinion surveys.

All responses were anonymous. Participants were required to complete every survey item, eliminating missing data due to nonresponse. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Board of North Carolina State University (Protocol #15529). Data analyses were conducted using SPSS version 26.0.

Instrumentation

The survey instrument was designed to assess public understanding of physician licensure, board certification, and board eligibility. It comprised three conceptual sections. First, participants responded to six Likert-type items (1 = Strongly Disagree to 4 = Strongly Agree) assessing beliefs and expectations regarding physicians' ongoing professional development (e.g., whether physicians should remain current and demonstrate continued competence). Second, participants were asked about their understanding of medical licensure and board certification. The initial item asked whether respondents knew the difference between licensure and certification. After responding, participants advanced to a new screen and could not revise their answer. Participants were then presented with standardized definitions drawn from the American Board of Medical Specialties (AMBS)²¹:

- *Medical licensure* was described as a state-granted legal requirement to practice medicine following residency training and completion of a general examination.

- *Board certification* was described as a voluntary, specialty-specific credential requiring additional training, examination, and ongoing assessment beyond licensure.

Participants then completed four additional items assessing perceptions of board certification and related behaviors. Finally, participants answered three items regarding awareness and interpretation of the term *board eligible*, including a multiple-response item capturing alternative meanings respondents associated with the designation. Demographic items included age, sex, race, Hispanic ethnicity, education, and geographic region.

Weighting and Analysis

Because mTurk samples differ systematically from the U.S. adult population, post-stratification weights were applied using 2017 U.S. Census benchmarks for age, sex, and race. Age was collapsed into four categories (18–29, 30–44, 45–59, ≥60 years). Sex was coded as male or female; respondents selecting an “other” option were excluded from weighted analyses. Race was categorized as White; Black or African American; American Indian/Alaska Native; Asian; and Native Hawaiian/Other Pacific Islander or other. Hispanic ethnicity was not used in weighting. Weights were calculated as the ratio of population to sample proportions within Age × Sex × Race cells and trimmed at a maximum value of 5 to limit variance inflation. All substantive results reported below are based on weighted analyses.

Results

All results presented below are based on analyses weighted to U.S. Census benchmarks for age, sex, and race. Unweighted distributions are reported only to describe the sample (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Survey Respondents (N = 806)

Characteristic	Unweighted n (%)	Weighted %
Age group		
18–29 years	214 (26.6)	18.8
30–44 years	351 (43.5)	17.6
45–59 years	171 (21.2)	15.9
≥60 years	70 (8.7)	47.7
Sex		
Female	481 (59.8)	49.5
Male	324 (40.2)	50.5
Race		
White	627 (80.0)	43.1
Black or African American	80 (10.2)	37.5
Asian	66 (8.4)	19.0
American Indian or Alaska Native	9 (1.1)	0.0
Native Hawaiian, Pacific Islander, or Other	2 (0.3)	0.4
Education		
High school or less	3 (0.9)	0.0
Some college	71 (20.6)	6.9
Bachelor’s degree	178 (51.6)	22.8

Graduate or professional degree	93 (27.0)	10.1
Total	806 (100.0)	100.0

Note. Unweighted values describe the observed survey sample. Weighted percentages reflect post-stratification adjustment to 2017 U.S. Census benchmarks for age, sex, and race. Percentages may not sum to 100 because of rounding. Respondents reporting a sex other than male or female were excluded from weighted analyses. Education was not used in the weighting procedure.

Public Expectations of Physicians’ Ongoing Professional Development

Respondents expressed exceptionally strong and consistent expectations regarding physicians’ ongoing professional development and demonstration of competence (Table 2). Agreement was near-universal across all items, with minimal disagreement observed. Virtually all respondents agreed or strongly agreed that physicians should stay up to date with advances in their specialty, with 98.8% indicating strong agreement and no respondents selecting “disagree.” Support remained similarly high when respondents were asked whether physicians should be *required* to stay current: 93.1% strongly agreed and 6.4% agreed, with fewer than 1% expressing strong disagreement.

Table 2. Public Expectations of Physicians’ Ongoing Professional Development

Item	SD, (%)	D, (%)	A, (%)	SA, (%)
Physicians should stay up to date with advances in their specialty	0.0	0.0	1.2	98.8
Physicians should be required to stay up to date	0.5	0.0	6.4	93.1
Physicians should demonstrate that they remain up to date	0.0	0.0	4.9	95.1
Physicians should be required to demonstrate ongoing competence	0.2	0.0	13.9	85.9
I expect my doctor to stay up to date with advances	1.5	0.0	1.1	97.4
I expect my doctor to participate in ongoing training and assessment	0.5	0.0	5.9	93.6

Note. Responses were measured on a 4-point Likert-type scale (SD = Strongly disagree; D = Disagree; A = Agree; SA = Strongly agree). Values represent weighted percentages and may not sum to 100 because of rounding.

Expectations extended beyond participation to accountability. A large majority of respondents (95.1%) strongly agreed that physicians should demonstrate that they remain up to date, and 85.9% strongly agreed that physicians should be required to demonstrate ongoing competence. Across these items, disagreement was rare and generally limited to fractions of a percent. Personal expectations closely mirrored these broader professional norms. Nearly all respondents reported that they expect their own doctor to stay up to date with advances in medicine (97.4% strongly agreed), and most expected their doctor to participate in ongoing training and assessment (93.6% strongly agreed). Taken together, these findings indicate broad public consensus that continued learning and demonstrable competence are core expectations of medical practice rather than discretionary activities.

Importance of Board Certification and Confidence in Board-Certified Physicians

Board certification was widely valued by respondents. Approximately 79% reported that it was either very important or somewhat important that their physician be board certified, including 38.4% who described board certification as very important. Only a small minority reported that certification was not at all important (1.9%). These attitudes were reflected in confidence judgments. An overwhelming majority of respondents indicated that they would have greater confidence in a physician who is board certified, with 67.8% reporting that certification would definitely increase confidence and an additional 28.2% indicating it would probably increase confidence. Fewer than 4% reported that board certification would not increase their confidence in a physician’s care.

Awareness of and Exposure to the Term “Board Eligible”

Awareness of the term *board eligible* was substantially lower than awareness of board certification. Approximately 28% of respondents reported familiarity with the term, while a clear majority reported that they were not aware of it. Likewise, nearly one in five respondents (18.7%) reported recalling having seen a physician describe themselves as board eligible, suggesting limited direct exposure to the designation among the general public.

Interpretation of the Term “Board Eligible”

Respondents’ interpretations of the term *board eligible* were heterogeneous and often overlapping (Table 3). The most frequently selected interpretation was that a physician had completed all requirements and was awaiting certification results (48.6%). Many respondents also believed the term indicated that a physician was in the process of certification and likely to be certified soon (38.6%). At the same time, substantial proportions of respondents attributed more ambiguous or divergent meanings to the designation. Nearly one-third (28.5%) interpreted *board eligible* as indicating that certification was in progress but without a clear timeframe. Others believed the term signified that a physician intended to pursue certification but had not yet begun (24.3%), or that the physician had no interest in becoming board certified (34.4%). Because respondents could select multiple interpretations, these views were not mutually exclusive, underscoring the lack of a shared public understanding of the term.

Table 3. Public Interpretation of the Term “Board Eligible”

Interpretation	Weighted %
Completed all requirements; awaiting certification result	48.6
In the process of certification and likely to be certified soon	38.6
In the process of certification, but timeframe is uncertain	28.5
Intends to pursue certification but has not yet begun	24.3
Has no interest in becoming board certified	34.4
May or may not decide to seek certification	2.4

Note. Respondents could select multiple interpretations; percentages therefore do not sum to 100. Values represent weighted percentages.

Summary of Findings

Taken together, the results reveal a clear contrast. Public expectations regarding physicians' professional development and the value of board certification were strong, consistent, and widely shared. In contrast, the meaning of *board eligible* was interpreted in multiple and sometimes conflicting ways, suggesting that the designation lacks a clear and consistently understood public meaning.

Discussion

This study provides a population-adjusted examination of U.S. adults' expectations regarding physician professionalism, their valuation of board certification, and their understanding of the term *board eligible*. The findings both reinforce and extend prior research on public perceptions of physician credentialing, while addressing a gap in the literature concerning how credentialing language is interpreted by patients.

Public Expectations of Professional Development

Respondents expressed near-unanimous expectations that physicians remain current in their specialty and demonstrate ongoing professional competence. These findings align closely with longstanding scholarship emphasizing licensure as a minimum threshold for practice rather than a comprehensive assurance of ongoing competence, and with broader conceptions of medicine as a self-regulating profession accountable to the public.^{3,5} Prior literature has argued that continued assessment and professional development serve not only a technical function but also a social one, reinforcing public trust in professional self-regulation.⁷

What is notable in the present study is the strength and consistency of these expectations across items. Disagreement was virtually absent, and expectations applied not only abstractly to physicians as a group but concretely to respondents' own doctors. This suggests that ongoing professional development is widely viewed by the public as a normative obligation intrinsic to medical practice rather than as an optional enhancement. These results provide empirical support for policy arguments that public trust in medicine is contingent on visible commitments to continued competence, rather than solely on initial licensure.

Board Certification as a Public Signal of Trust and Competence

Consistent with earlier population-based studies,¹¹⁻¹² board certification was strongly associated with perceived importance and confidence. Nearly all respondents indicated that certification would probably or definitely increase their confidence in a physician's care, and a substantial majority reported that certification itself was important in choosing a physician. These findings reinforce the view that board certification functions as an important public-facing signal of professionalism and competence, even when patients may not fully understand the technical requirements of certification.

The durability of this perception is notable given ongoing intra-professional debates about the costs, burdens, and evidentiary basis of maintenance of certification. While prior studies examining the relationship between certification and outcomes have produced mixed results,⁸⁻¹⁰ the present findings suggest that, from the public's perspective, board certification retains symbolic and practical significance as an indicator of physician quality. In this sense,

certification appears to fulfill a communicative role that complements—but is not reducible to—its technical assessment function.

Ambiguity in the Interpretation of “Board Eligible”

In contrast to the clarity surrounding board certification, respondents’ interpretations of *board eligible* were markedly heterogeneous. Although fewer respondents were familiar with the term or recalled encountering it, those who did interpret it ascribed multiple and sometimes contradictory meanings. While many respondents understood *board eligible* to indicate that certification was imminent or pending, substantial proportions believed it signaled uncertainty, delay, or even lack of intent to pursue certification.

This finding addresses a notable gap in the literature. Prior discussions of *board eligible* have largely occurred in regulatory, legal, or professional contexts, with limited empirical attention to how the term is understood by patients themselves. The present results offer direct evidence that *board eligible* lacks a consistent public meaning. Importantly, respondents frequently selected multiple interpretations, indicating not simply disagreement but genuine ambiguity about what the designation conveys.

Implications for Regulation, Ethics, and Professional Communication

The observed ambiguity surrounding *board eligible* provides empirical context for regulatory actions taken by some state medical boards to restrict the use of the term in physician advertising. Policies such as those adopted by the Texas Medical Board are grounded in concerns that *board eligible* may mislead patients by implying equivalence with board certification or by obscuring meaningful differences in credential status. The present findings support the premise underlying such regulations: namely, that the term does not reliably communicate a clear or bounded professional status to the public.

From an ethical standpoint, the results underscore the importance of transparency in professional self-presentation. Ethical analyses of physician advertising emphasize that claims about credentials should be truthful and not misleading, even when technically accurate. A designation that is well understood within the profession but interpreted inconsistently by patients may fail to meet that standard, regardless of intent. While this study does not adjudicate whether use of *board eligible* is unethical, it demonstrates that the term does not function as a clear informational cue for patients.

More broadly, these findings raise questions about the alignment between professional credentialing language and public understanding. By empirically demonstrating the divergence between professional intent and public interpretation, this study contributes evidence that has been largely assumed but rarely measured. Thus, if board certification communicates a clear and valued signal, while *board eligible* communicates ambiguity, the contrast suggests a need for greater intentionality in how credentialing pathways are described in public-facing contexts.

Strengths and Limitations

This study has several strengths, including its national scope, use of population-adjusted survey weights, and detailed assessment of public interpretations of physician credentialing. By distinguishing baseline awareness from informed perceptions and by reporting full response distributions for key items, the study provides a nuanced view of public expectations and interpretations.

Limitations should also be noted. Although weighting improves representativeness, the data derive from a non-probability online sample and should be interpreted accordingly. The findings reflect public perceptions at a single snapshot in time. Finally, the study focuses on perceptions rather than behaviors and does not examine how credential interpretations directly influence healthcare choices.

Conclusions

Taken together, the findings reveal a marked asymmetry in public understanding of physician credentials. Expectations regarding ongoing professional development and the value of board certification are strong, coherent, and widely shared. In contrast, the term *board eligible* is interpreted inconsistently and often ambiguously, limiting its usefulness as a communicative device for patients. These results suggest that greater clarity in credentialing language may help align professional self-regulation with public expectations for transparency and trust.

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